

building-integrated user-
empowered flexibility trading

Deliverable D8.1: Communication materials and website

WP8 – Dissemination and Communication

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PUBLIC

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the first set of marketing materials that will be used to support the communication and dissemination activities within BlueBird. It includes the description of the project visual identity, the project website, the social media profile that has been created, a first project flyer, and an overview of the created templates for presentations and documents (such as deliverables).

This is the first deliverable of WP8, and it complements *D8.2 - Dissemination and communication actions plans and target KPIs*, that describes how this material will be used during the project to reach the relevant stakeholders.

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I. VISUAL IDENTITY

I.1. Logo

For the branding of the project a logo was created, including a few variants (a horizontal, completely blue and completely white version). The logo will be used in all communication and dissemination actions, including the website, social media, flyers and posters, newsletters, presentations, deliverables, etc.

The different logo files are shared with the consortium via the project’s sharepoint.

Figure 1. BlueBird logo

Figure 2. BlueBird logo variants (horizontal, blue, white)

I.2. Templates

Templates have been created and distributed to all consortium partners for:

- Deliverables: a Word template, used for this deliverable, see also Figure 3. This template establishes a consistent style and format to ensure a professional presentation of the project results, and uniformity over all project deliverables.

- Presentation: a PowerPoint template for internal and external presentations, see Figure 4. This template ensures a consistent and professional visual identity in all project communications.

These templates are also available on the project’s sharepoint.

Figure 3. BlueBird deliverable template (Microsoft Word)

Figure 4. BlueBird presentation template (Microsoft PowerPoint)

I.3. Project flyers and posters

Different flyers and posters will be created throughout the project to communicate the main goals and outcomes from the project to the relevant stakeholders, on scientific and industrial conferences, workshops, fairs and other types of events.

A first flyer has been created (see Figure 5) highlighting the project context and key objectives, the different partners, and the 7 pilot environments, and has already been used for the BRIDGE General Assembly event on March 25-26 2025. The flyer has been published on BlueBird’s project community in Zenodo and it is available on the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/15118361>.

This flyer will also serve as template for future flyers and posters.

BlueBird Context

To achieve the EU’s Green Deal and sustainability targets, its power grid has seen a drastic increase renewable energy resources. This causes balancing the electricity supply and demand to be ever more challenging and calls for increased flexibility in the electricity system. Hence, flexibility schemes lie at the core of the EU’s holy grail to realize the required energy transition.

BlueBird focuses on unlocking such energy flexibility from buildings, and thus will deliver a comprehensive and validated toolset, to fully allow competitive adoption of buildings as energy flexibility assets. BlueBird’s toolset will build on standard ontologies to supporting a smooth integration of services towards energy market players (i.e., TSO, DSO, aggregators) while maximally aligning with end-user’s (i.e., building managers, occupants) requirements and acceptance criteria.

BlueBird Objectives

The project has 5 key objectives:

- Provide vmulti-carrier flexibility services for buildings, integrating energy and non-energy carriers, empowering end-users with control;
- Facilitate the flexibility trading between buildings and the energy market stakeholders;
- Evaluate BlueBird in 7 demonstrators with residential, public, commercial, office and industrial buildings;
- Maximize adoption based on (1) business models and successful value networks, and (2) a set of feasibility studies for on-site storage and renewables;
- Deliver a highly replicable, standardized, benefit-demonstrated Replicability Package.

Partners

For more information, please follow us on

[linkedin.com/company/bluebird-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/bluebird-project)

bluebird-project.eu

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BLUE BIRD

building-integrated user-empowered flexibility trading

BlueBird Business Cases

BlueBird has defined a wide range of targeted high-level services that form the core drivers for the technical developments. These services have been identified through a detailed analysis of 7 business cases across Europe, covering 24 use cases. Below, we summarize the business cases in terms of the available equipment, involved stakeholders, and how flexibility will be used.

To realize these services, BlueBird will deliver a toolset of hierarchical predictive control software, comprising a Trading Manager (to unlock flexibility and allow participation in energy markets), a Flexibility Manager (to jointly control assets at the building level), and interaction tools (to empower users and building managers).

#1 Karno

Karno (a Belgian zero-carbon district heating developer) will upgrade its 4th generation low-temperature (35 °C) network to improve integration in the electrical power grid. This includes (1) increasing flexibility by adapting to user behavior, (2) leveraging additional flex from storage and local PV, and (3) expanding the heating network.

#2 AMB

The metropolitan area of Barcelona (AMB) aims to leverage flexibility from public building systems (heat pumps for heating and/or cooling, gas-based heating) and EV chargers, to (1) optimize self-consumption of local PV and solar thermal, and/or (2) enable participation to the Iberian electricity markets (e.g., TOU-based).

#3 WeSmart

As an energy aggregator WeSmart wants to leverage EMS-based control within the energy community at the Tour & Taxis site in Brussels, Belgium. This will encompass (1) real-time data acquisition from end users’ smart meters, EV chargers and 10k rooftop PV panels, (2) recommendation-based DR from end users, and (3) validating economic viability accounting for user behavior.

#4 Enea Office

The Polish power company Enea will enable dynamic management of its office building’s cooling and heating system, fed by a municipal heating grid. This will encompass (1) predictive monitoring and control of the office’s and social rooms’ thermostats, and (2) providing users with thermostat settings accounting for their comfort.

#5 Enea Grid

As a 2nd case for Enea, it will maximally exploit flexibility of a high/medium voltage power station’s cooling and heating, with minimal impact on comfort and assuring safety of technical staff. BlueBird will realize (1) non-intrusive monitoring and AI-based predictive control, and (2) dynamic heating and cooling management to unlock flexibility.

#6 EK

The Austrian flexibility aggregator and service provider Energiekompass will market Wasserverband Südburgenland’s water works building’s battery and operational flex. This will entail (1) upgrading the automation system of the water tanks, (2) optimizing its operation and scheduling exploiting the tanks as energy storage, and (3) improving VPP capability and functionality.

#7 EWH

EWH, as a vertically integrated electricity supplier/DSO, generates electricity from local renewables and manages supply. EWH will exploit BlueBird technology to better manage its largest customers (i.e., hotels) to (1) identify and forecast their load and flexibility, and subsequently, (2) turn the hotels into smart-grid-ready buildings.

Figure 5. BlueBird flyer

II. PROJECT WEBSITE

The public project website is available on <https://bluebird-project.eu> and will be one of the main communication tools throughout the project. The website currently provides an overview of the project objectives, the 7 pilots and the different consortium partners. The website will gradually be extended to provide more details on the developed solutions for building flexibility, an overview of downloadable materials, such as project publications, press releases and public deliverables, and at least one blog post or news update per month written by the different project partners, with info on obtained results, participation in events, publications, etc.

All partners will use their communication channels in order to generate traffic to the BlueBird website and increase the visibility of the project.

Figure 6. BlueBird homepage

Figure 7. Overview of the BlueBird pilots on the website

Figure 8. Overview of the BlueBird consortium on the website

III. SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media will be used to raise awareness on project results, pilot validations, project events and publications. LinkedIn will be used as main social media channel as it gives the opportunity of enhancing two-way communication with well-defined professional groups of stakeholders.

The news items that will be posted on the website will also be published on the project LinkedIn page and reposted by the different project partners within their own LinkedIn networks.

The screenshot shows the LinkedIn profile for the BlueBird Project. The profile header features a decorative banner with a blue and yellow bird perched on a branch, with the text 'BLUE BIRD' below it. The profile name is 'BlueBird Project', with the tagline 'Building Integrated User Empowered Flexibility Trading'. It lists 'Research Services' and has 37 followers and 11-50 employees. A notification indicates that 'Chris & 5 other connections follow this page'. Action buttons for 'Message' and 'Following' are visible. The navigation menu includes 'Home', 'About', 'Posts', 'Jobs', and 'People'. The 'Posts' tab is active, showing a filter for 'All' and options for 'Images', 'Videos', 'Articles', and 'Documents'. The first post is dated '1mo' and contains the following text:

Last month, the Horizon Europe project BlueBird kicked off, aiming to revolutionize the use of energy flexibility assets in the electricity domain by harnessing cutting-edge AI and data solutions. Aligned with the ambitious objectives of the European Green Deal, BlueBird seeks to enhance sustainability, efficiency, and integration within the energy sector.

BlueBird's primary goal is to deliver a robust and validated toolset to support the competitive adoption of buildings as energy flexibility assets. By doing so, the project will facilitate seamless collaboration between energy market players such as Transmission System Operators, Distribution System Operators, and aggregators, while addressing the unique requirements and acceptance criteria of building managers and occupants.

The project will be trialed across seven large-scale demonstrators in five European countries — Spain, Belgium, Poland, Austria, and Germany. These demonstrators will include validation of end-user and beneficiary acceptance using innovative social-science methodologies.

To ensure long-term impact and replicability, BlueBird will compile a comprehensive package of lessons learned and actionable recommendations for future adoption. This guidance will emphasize sustainable industrial partnerships and ecosystem resilience, offering a roadmap for broader application across Europe.

BlueBird's ambitious objectives will be achieved by a consortium of seventeen experienced and complementary partners, bringing together expertise from research institutions, industrial leaders, public authorities, and NGOs across six European countries, and with the support of [CINEA - European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency](#):

Figure 9. Screenshot of the BlueBird LinkedIn page and first post.

